

A tail does not always make a difference: Assembly of cds nets from $\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2$ and 1,4-bis(*n*-alkoxy)-2,5-bis(3,2':6',3''-terpyridin-4'-yl)benzene ligands

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Figure S1. The structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{3})]_n \cdot 3.5n\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$, with symmetry generated atoms. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity; ellipsoids are plotted at 50% probability level. Symmetry codes: i = $-1-x, -1-y, -1-z$; ii = $1+x, y, 1+z$; iii = $-1-x, 1/2+y, -3/2-z$; iv = $-2-x, -1/2+y, -3/2-z$; v = $-2-x, -1-y, -2-z$; vi = $-2-x, 1/2+y, -3/2-z$.

Figure S2. The structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{4})]_n \cdot 5.5n\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$, with symmetry generated atoms. Hydrogen atoms and solvent molecules are omitted for clarity; ellipsoids are plotted at 50% probability level. Symmetry codes: $i = 1-x, 1-y, 2-z$; $ii = -1+x, y, 1+z$; $iii = -1+x, 1/2-y, 1/2+z$; $iv = x, 1/2-y, 1/2+z$; $v = 1-x, -1/2+y, 3/2-z$; $vi = 2-x, 1/2+y, 3/2-z$; $vii = 2-x, 1-y, 1-z$. The sulfur atoms S2, S4 and S6 of the $[\text{NCS}]^-$ units are disordered and have been modelled over sites of 50:30:20%, 60:20:20% and 70:30% occupancies, respectively, and only the major occupancy site is shown. The terminal unit in the $-\text{OButyl}$ chain on O3 is disordered and has been modelled over sites of 75% and 25% occupancies and only the major occupancy site is shown.

Figure S3. The structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{5})]_n \cdot 4n\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$, with symmetry generated atoms. Hydrogen atoms and solvent molecules are omitted for clarity; ellipsoids are plotted at 50% probability level. Symmetry codes: $i = 1-x, 1-y, 1-z$; $ii = x, y, 1+z$; $iii = \frac{1}{2}-x, \frac{1}{2}+y, \frac{1}{2}-z$; $iv = \frac{3}{2}-x, -\frac{1}{2}+y, \frac{1}{2}-z$; $v = 1-x, 1-y, -z$; $vi = \frac{3}{2}-x, \frac{1}{2}+y, \frac{1}{2}-z$.

Figure S4. The structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{6})]_n \cdot 3.8n\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$, with symmetry generated atoms. Hydrogen atoms and solvent molecules are omitted for clarity; ellipsoids are plotted at 50% probability level. Symmetry codes: $i = 1-x, 1-y, 2-z$; $ii = x, y, 1+z$; $iii = \frac{1}{2}-x, \frac{1}{2}+y, \frac{3}{2}-z$; $iv = \frac{3}{2}-x, -\frac{1}{2}+y, \frac{3}{2}-z$; $v = 1-x, 1-y, 1-z$; $vi = \frac{3}{2}-x, \frac{1}{2}+y, \frac{3}{2}-z$. The terminal units with C23 and C24 in the $-\text{OHexyl}$ chain are disordered and have been modelled over sites of 60% and 40% occupancies and only the major one is shown.

Figure S5. The structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{7})]_n \cdot 3.1n\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$, with symmetry generated atoms. Hydrogen atoms and solvent molecules are omitted for clarity; ellipsoids are plotted at 50% probability level. Symmetry codes: $i = 1-x, 1-y, 1-z$; $ii = x, y, -1+z$; $iii = 3/2-x, -1/2+y, 3/2-z$; $iv = 1/2-x, 1/2+y, 3/2-z$; $v = 1-x, 1-y, 2-z$; $vi = 1/2-x, -1/2+y, 3/2-z$. The terminal units with C22, C23, C24 and C25 in the -Oheptyl chain are disordered and have been modelled over sites of 50% and 50% occupancies and only one of the equal occupancy sites is shown. The sulfur S2 of the $[\text{NCS}]^-$ unit is disordered and has been modelled over sites of 80% and 20% occupancies and only the major occupancy site is shown.

Figure S6. The structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{8})]_n \cdot 1.6n\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2n\text{MeOH}$, with symmetry generated atoms. Hydrogen atoms and solvent molecules are omitted for clarity; ellipsoids are plotted at 50% probability level. Symmetry codes: i = $-x, 1-y, 1-z$; ii = $x, y, 1+z$; iii = $-1/2-x, 1/2+y, 1/2-z$; iv = $1/2-x, -1/2+y, 1/2-z$; v = $-x, 1-y, -z$; vi = $1/2-x, 1/2+y, 1/2-z$. The sulfur atom S2 of the $[\text{NCS}]^-$ unit is disordered and has been modelled over sites of 80% and 20% occupancies and only the major occupancy site is shown.

Figure S7. The solid-state FT-IR spectrum of $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{3})]_n \cdot 3.5n\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$.

Figure S8. The solid-state FT-IR spectrum of $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{4})]_n \cdot 5.5n\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$.

Figure S9. The solid-state FT-IR spectrum of $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{5})]_n \cdot 4n\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$.

Figure S10. The solid-state FT-IR spectrum of $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{6})]_n \cdot 3.8n\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$.

Figure S11. The solid-state FT-IR spectrum of $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{7})]_n \cdot 3.1n\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$.

Figure S12. The solid-state FT-IR spectrum of $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{8})]_n \cdot 1.6n\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2n\text{MeOH}$.

Figure S13. Overlay of the experimental (blue) PXRD (298 K) for the bulk material and that predicted (black) from the single crystal structure (150 K) of $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{3})]_n \cdot 3.5n\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$.

Figure S14. Overlay of the experimental (blue) PXRD (298 K) for the bulk material and that predicted (black) from the single crystal structure (150 K) of $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{4})]_n \cdot 5.5\text{nC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$.

Figure S15. TGA and mass spectrometric traces for the analysis of $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{3})]_n \cdot 3.5\text{nC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$. Red: temperature vs. time; black: weight of sample vs. time; dark blue: mass detection for m/z 146, 148 and 111; orange: mass detection for m/z 31.0.

Figure S16. TGA and mass spectrometric traces for the analysis of $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{4})]_n \cdot 5.5n\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$. Red: temperature vs. time; black: weight of sample vs. time; dark blue: mass detection for m/z 146, 148 and 111; orange: mass detection for m/z 31.0.

Figure S17. TGA and mass spectrometric traces for the analysis of $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{6})]_n \cdot 3.8n\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$. Red: temperature vs. time; black: weight of sample vs. time; dark blue: mass detection for m/z 146, 148 and 111; orange: mass detection for m/z 31.0.